

Appendix 1

Search terms dialogue

List of Query used in various databases

Database	Query
PubMed	<p>((("ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE"[All Fields] OR "MACHINE LEARNING"[All Fields] OR "DEEP LEARNING"[All Fields]) AND ("education, medical"[MeSH Terms] OR ("education"[All Fields] AND "medical"[All Fields]) OR "medical education"[All Fields] OR ("medical"[All Fields] AND "education"[All Fields]))) AND ("UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS"[All Fields] OR ("physician s"[All Fields] OR "physicians"[MeSH Terms] OR "physicians"[All Fields] OR "physician"[All Fields] OR "physicians s"[All Fields]))) AND ((("ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE"[All Fields] OR "MACHINE LEARNING"[All Fields] OR "DEEP LEARNING"[All Fields]) AND ("education, medical"[MeSH Terms] OR ("education"[All Fields] AND "medical"[All Fields]) OR "medical education"[All Fields] OR ("medical"[All Fields] AND "education"[All Fields]))) AND ("UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS"[All Fields] OR ("physician s"[All Fields] OR "physicians"[MeSH Terms] OR "physicians"[All Fields] OR "physician"[All Fields] OR "physicians s"[All Fields]))) AND ((classicalarticle[Filter] OR clinicalstudy[Filter] OR comparativestudy[Filter] OR observationalstudy[Filter]) AND (fft[Filter]) AND (english[Filter]) AND (2016:2023[pdat]))</p> <p>Results 633</p>
Google Scholar	<p>("ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE"OR"MACHINE LEARNING"OR"DEEP LEARNING")AND(MEDICAL EDUCATION)AND("UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS"OR PHYSICIANS))</p> <p>Results 17600 .took the first 100 results</p>
Scopus	<p>("artificial intelligence "OR "deep learning" OR "machine learning")AND ("Medical education" OR "Medical training")AND ("undergraduate students" OR "Medical staff" OR residents OR Trainees)</p> <p>Results 485</p>
ScienceDirect	<p>("artificial intelligence "OR "deep learning" OR "machine learning")AND ("Medical education" OR "Medical training")AND ("undergraduate students" OR "Medical staff" OR "residents OR Trainees)</p> <p>(295 studies).</p>

PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematics Reviews and Meta-Analysis) flow diagram

